

Ant photos

Article title: **Partner fidelity and environmental filtering preserve stage-specific turtle ant gut symbioses for over 40 million years**

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Photos of all ants included in this study

Cephalotes aff. *bimaculatus*: colony JS-C-220

Cephalotes aff. *wheeleri*: colony JS-C-211

JS3092-W1

JS3092-W2

JS3092-W3

JS3092-W4

JS3092-W5

JS3092-W6

JS3092-W7

JS3092-W8

JS3093-S1

JS3093-S2

JS3093-S3

JS3093-S4

JS3093-S5

JS3093-S6

JS3093-S7

JS3093-S8

JS3094-L1

JS3094-L2

JS3094-L3

JS3094-L4

JS3094-L5

JS3094-L6

JS3094-L7

JS3094-L8

Cephalotes depressus: colony C15-25

C15-25-W1

C15-25-W2

C15-25-W3

C15-25-W4

C15-25-S1

C15-25-S2

C15-25-S3

C15-25-S4

C15-25-C1

C15-25-C2

C15-25-Q1

C15-25-L1

C15-25-L2

C15-25-L3

C15-25-L4

C15-25-L5

C15-25-L6

C15-25-L7

C15-25-L8

Cephalotes goniodontus: colony JS-3-203

JS3026-W1

JS3026-W2

JS3026-W3

JS3026-W4

JS3026-C1

JS3026-C2

JS3026-C3

JS3024-Q1

JS3024-Q2

JS3024-Q3

JS3024-Q4

JS3024-M1

JS3024-M2

JS3024-M3

JS3023-L1

JS3023-L2

JS3023-L3

JS3023-L4

JS3023-L5

JS3023-L6

JS3023-L7

JS3023-L8

Cephalotes grandinosus: colony C15-21

C15-21-W1

C15-21-W2

C15-21-W3

C15-21-W4

C15-21-W5

C15-21-S1

C15-21-L1

C15-21-L2

C15-21-L4

C15-21-L5

Cephalotes grandinosus: colony C15-44

C15-44-W1

C15-44-W2

C15-44-W3

C15-44-W4

C15-44-C1

C15-44-C2

C15-44-S1

C15-44-S2

C15-44-S3

C15-44-S4

C15-44-Q1

C15-44-L1

C15-44-L2

C15-44-L3

C15-44-L4

C15-44-L5

C15-44-L6

Cephalotes maculatus: colony C15-28

C15-28-W1

C15-28-W2

C15-28-W3

C15-28-W4

C15-28-S1

C15-28-S2

C15-28-S3

C15-28-S4

C15-28-C1

C15-28-C2

C15-28-Q1

C15-28-L1

C15-28-L2

C15-28-L3

C15-28-L4

C15-28-L5

C15-28-L6

C15-28-L7

C15-28-L8

Cephalotes pusillus: colony C15-40

C15-40-W1

C15-40-W2

C15-40-W3

C15-40-W4

C15-40-S1

C15-40-S2

C15-40-S3

C15-40-S4

C15-40-Q1

C15-40-L1

C15-40-L2

C15-40-L3

C15-40-L4

C15-40-L5

C15-40-L6

C15-40-L7

C15-40-L8

Cephalotes setulifer: colony SRCset1

SRCset1-A1

SRCset1-A2

SRCset1-A3

SRCset1-A4

SRCset1-A5

SRCset1-A6

SRCset1-A7

SRCset1-A8

SRCset1-S1

SRCset1-S2

SRCset1-S3

SRCset1-Q1

SRCset1-L1

SRCset1-L2

SRCset1-L3

SRCset1-L4

SRCset1-L5

SRCset1-P1

SRCset1-P2

SRCset1-P3

SRCset1-P4

SRCset1-P5

Cephalotes setulifer: colony SRCset2

SRCset2-A1

SRCset2-A2

SRCset2-A3

SRCset2-A4

SRCset2-A5

SRCset2-A6

SRCset2-A7

SRCset2-A8

SRCset2-S1

SRCset2-S2

SRCset2-Q1

SRCset2-Q2

SRCset2-Q3

SRCset2-Q4

SRCset2-L1

SRCset2-L2

SRCset2-L3

SRCset2-L4

SRCset2-L5

SRCset2-L6

SRCset2-L7

SRCset2-L8

SRCset2-P1

SRCset2-P2

SRCset2-P3

Cephalotes targionii: colony C15-20

C15-20-W1

C15-20-W2

C15-20-W3

C15-20-W4

C15-20-C1

C15-20-S1

C15-20-S2

C15-20-S3

C15-20-S4

C15-20-L1

C15-20-L2

C15-20-L3

C15-20-L4

C15-20-L5

C15-20-L6

Cephalotes texanus: colony JS-C-235

JS3260-W1

JS3260-W2

JS3260-W3

JS3260-W4

JS3261-S1

JS3261-S2

JS3261-S3

JS3261-S4

JS3262-L1

JS3262-L2

JS3262-L3

JS3262-L4

Cephalotes unimaculatus: colony C16-08

C16-08-W1

C16-08-W2

C16-08-W3

C16-08-W4

C16-08-C1

C16-08-C2

C16-08-L1

C16-08-L2

C16-08-L3

C16-08-L4

C16-08-L5

C16-08-L6

C16-08-L7

C16-08-L8

Cephalotes varians: colony YH083

Cephalotes varians: colony YH091

Cephalotes varians: colony YH092

YH092_A04 YH092_A03 YH092_A01 YH092_A02 YH092_A06 YH092_A05 YH092_A07 YH092_A11 YH092_A08 YH092_A09 YH092_A10

YH092_A12 YH092_A15 YH092_A14 YH092_A13 YH092_A16 YH092_A21 YH092_A20 YH092_A19 YH092_A17 YH092_A18

YH092_L01 YH092_L04 YH092_L02 YH092_L03 YH092_L07 YH092_L05 YH092_L06 YH092_L08 YH092_L18 YH092_L17 YH092_L19

YH092_L20 YH092_L21

YH092_L09* YH092_L10* YH092_L11* YH092_L12* YH092_L13* YH092_L14* YH092_L15* YH092_L16*

YH092_P01 YH092_P02 YH092_P03 YH092_P04 YH092_P05 YH092_P06 YH092_P07 YH092_P08 YH092_P09 YH092_P10 YH092_P11

YH092_P12 YH092_P13 YH092_P14

Cephalotes varians: colony YH100

